

Shutdown Margin Calculations with SIMULATE5

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ABSTRACT

The SIMULATE5 advanced nodal code calculates the BWR shutdown margins always in 3D configuration with the full core height to take into account the axial rod composition. To speed up the evaluation, which typically must be done for large number of steps and over hundreds of control blades, a 3-step methodology with increasing accuracy is implemented in SIMULATE5. In this paper, the accuracy of the solution techniques is evaluated for the partially loaded cores during the reactor refueling. The fastest evaluation technique shows satisfactory agreement with the standard SIMULATE5 advanced solution. In addition, the validation of the SIMULATE5 SDM calculations for the partially loaded cores and for fully loaded cores at BOC and EOC is done for 2D cores against the CASMO5 transport solver. The eigenvalue discrepancies are mostly below 200 pcm and larger errors are observed only for cores with the highest number of water holes.

Keywords: SDM, BWR, reload, SIMULATE5

1. INTRODUCTION

The shutdown margin (SDM) calculations are an important part of the BWR core loading design, and must be analyzed for large number of steps and control blades configurations, including the reactor refueling and the startup schedules. Therefore, SDM evaluation needs to be fast and accurate for various core configurations including partially loaded cores and cold conditions. The SIMULATE5 advanced nodal code implements a 3-step methodology for a very fast evaluation of all control blades and identifying the configurations with smallest SDM, which are then recalculated with more accurate methods.

In this study, this methodology is tested for a fully loaded core and for a real refueling schedule of a large BWR reactor. In addition, the accuracy of eigenvalue solution of SIMULATE5 for the partially loaded cores is tested against the CASMO5 MOC solver.

2. SIMULATE5 METHODOLOGY

SIMULATE5 is an advanced nodal code which solves the 3D multi-group diffusion equation using an analytical nodal method and on-the-fly rehomogenization of nodal cross sections. The rehomogenization is based on flux solution obtained from a refined 1D axial and 2D radial geometry. In the axial direction, all the heterogeneities due to spacers, control rods, enrichment and burnable absorbers are therefore explicitly treated. In the radial direction, each assembly is divided into a submesh of 5x5 by default. The nodal cross sections and discontinuity factors are updated based on these 1D and 2D fluxes.

The SDM is defined as the difference between the critical eigenvalue and the eigenvalue obtained if all control rods are fully inserted except the highest-worth rod, which is fully withdrawn. Identifying the highest-worth rod means that all the combinations must be evaluated.

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Since this calculation is relatively computationally expensive, a faster evaluation is used for the SDM predictions. It is based on a hierarchical 3-step methods with increasing accuracy as follows [1]:

- Isotropic Buckling calculation (IsoBuc) using the node-wise 2-group cross sections, performed in a 3D mini-core configuration.
- Multi-group Analytic Nodal Method (ANM) in the same mini-core configuration.
- Multi-group ANM in full core configuration.

The first calculation is very fast and is performed for each evaluated control blade. The next two steps are performed only if the SDM calculated by the previous method is below a user-specified threshold.

The computational time needed for the individual steps rapidly increases – the Isotropic Buckling can be evaluated in approximately 0.1 s while the full core ANM is about 2 orders of magnitude slower. The error of the Isotropic Buckling eigenvalue is typically a few hundred pcm, therefore the more accurate ANM methods should be used to reevaluate the SDM of control rods where the SDM calculated by the fast Isotropic Buckling method is lower than a certain threshold.

The mini-core is constructed around the evaluated control rod, assuming that the worth of the control rod quickly decreases in the radial direction. By default, the mini-core size is 5 assemblies in each radial direction. In the axial direction, the mini-core is always constructed with the full core height to take into account the axial rod composition.

CASMO5 is an advanced lattice physics code [2-4], used to generate the cross-section library for SIMULATE5. It can also model a 2D MxN assembly geometry, providing transport theory reference results for SIMULATE5 validation.

The library for SIMULATE5 is generated by CASMO5 with the default modeling options, i.e. the 2D MOC calculation is done in 19 energy groups and with transport corrected P0 scattering, for both the fuel and the reflector segments. The data generated for the reflector are also used for the empty fuel locations filled with water.

The reference CASMO5 results were obtained with the same default options.

3. CORE DESCRIPTION

The validation of SIMULATE5's SDM calculations for the partially loaded cores is presented in sections 4 and 5 for the partially loaded cores based on a real reactor reload sequence and in section 6 for a fully loaded core of the same reactor. It is a large BWR reactor with 748 assemblies of the GE14 type with 10x10 rods (Figure 1). The fuel enrichment varies from 2.4 to 4.9% and the assemblies contain 12 – 15 gadolinium rods. The maximum burnup is 52.5 MWd/kg. The control blade absorber material is B4C. These calculations were done at cold conditions of 20°C.

The validation against CASMO5 was done for a 2D core established from the nodes in the middle of the reactor. The fuel movement steps are based on a realistic BWR core refueling sequence with over 2000 steps. This study shows results for about 700 steps, skipping the first hundreds of steps when the fuel is being unloaded (Figure 2). For each step, the eigenvalues calculated by CASMO5 and SIMULATE5 are compared for the all-rod-in (ARI) condition and the ARI except the maximum-worth rod (ARI-M) condition (maximum worth as predicted by SIMULATE5).

Figure 1. Core layout during the reshuffling.

Figure 2. Number of water holes and fresh fuel assemblies in the core

4. VALIDATION FOR 2D PARTIALLY LOADED CORES

The full core eigenvalues calculated by CASMO5 MxN using the code default settings are shown in Figures 3 and 4 for the ARI and ARI-M (highest worth rod withdrawn) cases respectively. In this reference CASMO5 calculations, the MOC solver was run with 19 energy groups and with transport corrected P0 scattering.

For a few steps (at the beginning and at the end of the shuffling, two steps in the regions where the eigenvalue changes rapidly, and one step in a region with almost constant eigenvalue), the calculation was repeated with higher number of groups and with the P3 scattering. The results are summarized in Table I.

Regarding the P0 calculations, the 95 group results are about 100 – 200 pcm lower and the 35 group results are about 50 pcm lower than the default 19 group ones.

The results with 35 groups and P3 scattering are about 100 – 200 pcm higher than the default ones and about 150 – 250 pcm higher than the 35 groups P0. The P3 scattering seems to have slightly higher impact than the number of groups.

The SIMULATE5 results were compared to the default CASMO5 solution, and the differences are shown in Figures 3 and 4 and Table I. SIMULATE5 by default uses 2 energy groups and its results are underpredicting CASMO5 mostly within 200 pcm, but the discrepancy is up to 300 pcm in the steps 800 – 1000. These are the core configurations with largest numbers of water holes and with the assemblies with largest reactivities located close to each other and closely surrounded by the water holes. When using 4 groups, the average error is almost half compared to 2 groups.

Table I. Eigenvalue differences between SIMULATE5 and CASMO5 for 2D full core; values marked in red are based on a limited number of calculations (10 in total) due to high run time requirements.

Model	Average k-eff	Average k-eff diff (pcm)	RMS diff (pcm)	Max diff (pcm)	Min diff (pcm)
C5 19g p0 (def)	0.97408				
C5 35g p0		-50	52		
C5 35g p3		139	149		
C5 95g p0		-136	140		
S5 2g	0.97264	-145	153	84	-311
S5 4g	0.97338	-70	81	177	-141

Figure 3. ARI 2D eigenvalue – reference C5 MxN run with default settings and the differences of SIMULATE5 and of CASMO5 with finer settings

Figure 4. ARI-M 2D eigenvalue – reference C5 MxN run with default settings and the differences of SIMULATE5 and of CASMO5 with finer settings

5. VALIDATION OF SIMULATE5 SDM 3-STEP METHODOLOGY

To evaluate the accuracy of the SIMULATE5 SDM 3-step methods, the results of the simplified methods are compared to the standard SIMULATE5 solution technique. The comparison is performed for a real reactor shuffling schedule and additionally for the 2D full core used in section 4. This 2D configuration allows for an additional comparison with CASMO5 results.

The SDM predicted by the standard solution method of SIMULATE5 (marked ANM_full) are in good agreement with the CASMO5 values, with maximum difference of 0.3% (Figure 5 and Table II). The simplified ANM_mini results are very close to the ANM_full results, with maximum difference of 0.03%. The fast IsoBuc evaluation is systematically overpredicting the SDM values, the bias is between 0.6 and 1.0%.

Table II. SDM differences between different methods for a 2D full core.

Model	Average SDM (%)	Average SDM diff (abs %)	Std dev diff (abs %)	RMS diff (abs %)	Max diff (abs %)	Min diff (abs %)
S5 ANM_full	1.83					
S5 ANM_mini	1.83	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	-0.02
S5 IsoBuc	2.72	0.89	0.06	0.89	0.97	0.62
C5 19g p0	1.82	-0.01	0.08	0.08	0.29	-0.08

Figure 5. SDM differences between different methods for a 2D full core

The comparison for a real 3D configuration is presented in Figure 6 and Table III. The ANM_mini solution predicts very similar values as the standard solution method of SIMULATE5; the absolute difference is below 0.1%.

The IsoBuc evaluation is very fast, about 2 orders of magnitude faster than the full core ANM calculation. The predicted values have a certain bias. In this study, the observed bias is between 0.5 – 0.8% for most of core configurations.

Table III. SDM differences between different methods for a real core shuffling sequence.

Model	Average SDM (%)	Average SDM diff (abs %)	Std dev diff (abs %)	RMS diff (abs %)	Max diff (abs %)	Min diff (abs %)
S5 ANM_full	1.87					
S5 ANM_mini	1.88	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	-0.01
S5 IsoBuc	2.55	0.69	0.12	0.70	0.80	0.23

Figure 6. SDM differences between different methods for a real core shuffling sequence

6. VALIDATION FOR 2D FULLY LOADED CORES

Full core SDM evaluation is performed for a representative cycle of the same reactor. Operational and design data from the BWR core model were used to create a 3D SIMULATE5 core-follow model. The selected cycle featured heavy Gd loading, with Gd content between 6 and 7 w/o, and multiple bundles with asymmetric loading. Axial plane # 10 was selected from the 3D SIMULATE5 model to study the SDM calculations. All CASMO5 and SIMULATE5 calculations were in full core symmetry. Calculations were performed at two exposure points: the beginning of the cycle (BOC) and the end of the cycle (EOC). Both CASMO5 MxN and SIMULATE5 models were consistently initialized using single-assembly CASMO5 calculations. The depleted fuel assembly exposures and void histories were taken from axial plane 10 of the 3D SIMULATE5 core-follow model. CASMO5 multi-assembly calculations were run with 95 energy groups and with transport corrected P0 scattering.

First, SIMULATE5 SDM calculations are run on a 3D core to locate the minimum SDM. Seven different 2D, full-core, CASMO5 MxN calculations are run: the first case represents the BOC global cold critical case, and the remaining six represent the SDM cases for selected rods along the diagonal symmetry axes of the North-West quarter core, including the rod with the minimum SDM. Similarly, eight additional 2D full-core calculations are performed for the EOC SDM cases.

Table IV presents eigenvalue comparisons between the two-group and four-group SIMULATE5 and CASMO5 MxN for the cold-critical and SDM cases. The maximum difference in the eigenvalue between SIMULATE5 and CASMO5 is less than 200 pcm. The difference between the two-group and four-group SIMULATE5 eigenvalues is less than 100 pcm at BOC and less than 200 pcm at EOC. The four-group SIMULATE5 model offers a slightly smaller standard deviation.

Figure 7 compares the SDM with two-group SIMULATE5 vs the CASMO5 multi-assembly. The agreement between the SIMULATE5 computed SDM and the CASMO5 MxN is excellent, with a maximum difference of less than 0.11% in all configurations and less than 0.6% for the rod with the minimum SDM.

Table IV. Eigenvalue comparisons in pcm between SIMULATE5 and CASMO5 for a fully loaded cores.

	BOC		EOC	
	2 group	4 group	2 group	4 group
Cold Critical	-95	-12	-95	-12
SDM #1	-112	-2	31	189
SDM #2	-78	-38	-82	127
SDM #3	-156	-50	-74	136
SDM #4	-162	-41	-60	146
SDM #5	-154	-37	-38	167
SDM #6	-151	29	-55	153
SDM #7			-30	176
SDM #8			-65	144
	-129 ± 33	-23 ± 30	-47 ± 36	155 ± 21

